

KREDIT TIZIMI ORQALI TALABALARNI IJODIY FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI

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Annatotsiya. Maqolada ta’lim kredit modul tizimida talabalarni mustaqil imkoniyatini yaratilishi modul tizimida talabalarning ijodiy faoliyatini rejalashtirish jarayoni katta ahamiyati, ijodiy faoliyatning eng muhim belgisi uning amalga oshirilishi natijasida bilim, ko’nikma, malaka, shaxsning ijodiy qobiliyatlari paydo bo’lishi ekanligini yoritilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Modul-kredit, ta’lim-tarbiya, ijodiy faoliyatini, texnologiya, rivojlanish, pedagogik jarayon, talaba, mustaqil izlanish.

Аннотация. В статье подчеркивается большое значение процесса планирования творческой деятельности студентов в модульной системе создания самостоятельных возможностей студентов в модульной системе образовательных кредитов, а важнейшим признаком творческой деятельности является появление знаний, умений, квалификации, и творческие способности личности как результат ее реализации.

Ключевые слова: Кредитный модуль, образование, творческая деятельность, технология, развитие, педагогический процесс, студент, самостоятельное исследование.

Annotation: The article highlights the great importance of the process of planning students' creative activities in the module system of creating independent opportunities for students in the educational credit module system, and the most important sign of creative activity is the emergence of knowledge, skills, qualifications, and creative abilities of the individual as a result of its implementation.

Key words: Credit module, education, creative activity, technology, development, pedagogical process, student, independent research.

Our republic includes creative activities in distance education as a means of increasing the overall educational efficiency of students and personal self-realization. Building the pedagogical foundations of this process involves considering the nature of creative activity of students using the credit system and building a system of organizational and pedagogical actions of all subjects of distance education in accordance with this activity.